

Communication breakdown: Gaze-based prediction of system error for an AI-assisted robotic arm simulated in VR

Björn R. Severitt
bjoern.severitt@uni-tuebingen.de
University of Tübingen
Tübingen, Germany

Patrizia Lenhart
patrizia.lenhart@student.uni-tuebingen.de
University of Tübingen
Tübingen, Germany

Benedikt W. Hosp
benedikt.hosp@uni-tuebingen.de
University of Tübingen
Tübingen, Germany

Nora Castner
nora.castner@zeiss.com
Carl Zeiss Vision International GmbH
Aalen, Germany

Siegfried Wahl
siegfried.wahl@uni-tuebingen.de
University of Tübingen
Tübingen, Germany
Carl Zeiss Vision International GmbH
Aalen, Germany

Figure 1: Experimental paradigm of gaze-based interaction for target selection where system errors are gradually incorporated over time. First, all possible targets are released, with a yellow ball being the true target. Second, the true target is selected by the system based on the user's gaze. Third, the robotic arm destroys the target. Finally, the robot arm returns to its starting position.

ABSTRACT

Neurological degenerative conditions can affect motor functions, making mobility daunting. Recent configurations of mobility devices that leverage artificial intelligence (AI) show its ability to handle complex information like user input. We create a virtual reality environment to measure participants' reactions to correct and incorrect feedback from an AI-assistance system. Using gaze to evaluate these reactions, we investigate whether we can automatically predict an upcoming system error. Our results show that gaze reactions occur within 300 ms when the system highlights user input, but the delay extends to 1 second without highlighting.

Subject dependent gaze behavior proved complicated for developing a generalizable model based on previous work using TCNs for online recognition of upcoming errors. Therefore, more adaptable models for individuals may be a better alternative for gaze-based accessibility systems.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Human-centered computing** → **Human computer interaction (HCI)**; • **Computing methodologies** → *Feature selection*; Computer vision representations; • **Applied computing** → *Psychology*.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution International 4.0 License.

ETRA '24, June 04–07, 2024, Glasgow, United Kingdom
© 2024 Copyright held by the owner/author(s).
ACM ISBN 979-8-4007-0607-3/24/06
<https://doi.org/10.1145/3649902.3653339>

KEYWORDS

Accessibility, Eye movements and cognition, Error Prediction, Gaze Interaction, Machine Learning

ACM Reference Format:

Björn R. Severitt, Patrizia Lenhart, Benedikt W. Hosp, Nora Castner, and Siegfried Wahl. 2024. Communication breakdown: Gaze-based prediction of system error for an AI-assisted robotic arm simulated in VR. In *2024 Symposium on Eye Tracking Research and Applications (ETRA '24), June 04–07, 2024, Glasgow, United Kingdom*. ACM, New York, NY, USA, 7 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3649902.3653339>

1 INTRODUCTION

Robotic limbs that facilitate motor abilities can foster independence and wellbeing in persons with degenerative neurological conditions. At present, these mobile assistance technologies are poised for a renaissance with the recent advances in artificial intelligence (AI). Already, AI has created accessibility improvements for this community via rehabilitation [Andras et al. 2020; Lee et al. 2022; Zhou et al. 2020], exoskeletons [Zhu et al. 2021], wearables [Wang et al. 2018; Wen et al. 2021], and wheelchair navigation [Sakai et al. 2019; Zgallai et al. 2019]. These systems can rely on gaze-based input, and AI has the potential to form higher level abstractions from it to gain better understanding of the user.

Gaze as a modality for system communication has been become more sophisticated over the past 40 years [Jacob and Stellmach 2016; Majaranta and Riiha 2002]. It leverages natural and intuitive eye movements relative to a task or goal, though can be susceptible to known issues like the midas touch problem and signal inaccuracies [Barz et al. 2018; Jacob and Karn 2003]. Despite its drawbacks, it has made major contributions towards usability and accessibility in certain communities. For instance, eye typing to enable communication for people with loss of speech [Majaranta and Riiha 2002], wheelchair navigation via eye movements for people who have minimized mobility [Subramanian et al. 2019]. More broadly, gaze controlled systems can offer seamless recognition of task behavior [Bektař et al. 2023], situational context [Lukashova-Sanz et al. 2022], and user states [Hirzle et al. 2020; Parisay et al. 2020] or intention recognition [Belardinelli 2023; Penzkofer et al. 2023] at any given moment. These aspects can promote accessibility since they strive for a more natural interaction, where such high level understanding is more implicitly inferred by the system. Incorporating AI in gaze-based interaction traverses both the system and the user sides of the communication: How AI translates user input and how users recognize how the AI has interpreted their input.

This work focuses on AI's impact on interaction with accessibility support devices, namely communication via a user's attention and gaze behavior and, more prominent, how the user reacts when the system has falsely interpreted a user's intentions. We explore how gaze features can predict a user's recognition of an upcoming error in the system's action execution. We build upon previous exploratory findings that indicate gaze features can be robust predictors of a user's intentions to terminate a movement. This paper presents the following contributions: (1) Design of a Virtual Reality (VR) simulation that emulates an interactive scenario involving a robotic arm supported by AI to understand the reaction of people to errors. (2) Evaluation of perceptual vs. the motor reaction to errors based on the interface visualization system. (3) Using the gaze features as predictors to determine system errors in an online setup.

2 RELATED WORK

Confident interaction with assistive robotic systems can be challenging because of strong individual factors, such as users' understanding of a system's capabilities and their expectations [Kok and Soh 2020]. Some users of such a system tend to distrust it, others tend to over-trust these systems, even in situations where the system is clearly wrong [Booth et al. 2017; Krber et al. 2018]. A system that is more transparent to the user therefore gives them a more effective way to self-correct [Mark and Kobsa 2005]. Some research has incorporated AI for explainability, which improved interaction on aspects such as understandability and trust [Leichtmann et al. 2023].

But what if the AI-assisted system makes an error? Previous studies have shown that summarized eye tracking statistics can predict intention to act [Bovo et al. 2020; David-John et al. 2021] as well as errors [Bovo et al. 2020; Bruder et al. 2016; Severitt et al. 2023]. Many of these error prediction studies have focused on user errors. However, other types of errors also affect interaction; the errors that are made by the system, known as input recognition errors. This can affect realtime interaction. Since we want a system that works in realtime, finding features and methods that enable fast prediction of errors is necessary. To tackle this problem, [Peacock et al. 2022] was able to distinguish between input recognition errors and user-initiated input actions as early as 50 and up to 550 milliseconds after selection with linear regression models. [Aronson and Admoni 2018] were able to show in a human-robot study that the gaze of a human can be interesting for error prediction. They found that the user's gaze deviates from the usual patterns as soon as an error is made by the system, such as the robot's elbows.

Now, finding the most appropriate gaze features in such small time frames is still challenging. Building off of the work by [Peacock et al. 2022], one method proposed by [Sendhilnathan et al. 2022] differentiated between different phases (user errors, input recognition errors and intention prediction) using a temporal convolution network (TCN). Using the first-order deviation of the x, y and z axis eye-data as input, they achieved a performance of up to 68% predicting the phases with 33% being chance level. To the best of our knowledge, this is the only paper that offers prediction of input recognition errors in a realtime setup. Thus, we feel it is an applicable approach for our current system.

In our previous research [Severitt et al. 2023], we modeled a robot-assisted task in VR where trajectory collisions needed to be avoided by user input. Gaze-based features such as mean fixation duration and saccade velocity showed significant effects for the scenarios where a collision occurred and the user terminated the trajectory. Furthermore, a random forest classifier could predict the intention to terminate with an accuracy of 86%. We build upon this work by assessing the generalizability of the gaze features in a realtime setup.

Therefore, the current work focuses on gaze features that can be computed in a short time window, which we analyze directly after the robot arm starts movement. We believe that we can find error-distinguishing features in this time window and create a classifier for detecting errors based on eye movement. We also assess how visualizing the AI system's translation of the user's gaze effects interaction. Via target highlighting, the participant

knows, immediately after selecting the target, whether the system has correctly understood their intention. We therefore assume that there are eye movement reaction differences related to visualization in this time window.

3 METHODS

3.1 Participants

Thirty seven participants were recruited via word of mouth and email lists. Twenty participants (14 men, 6 women, $M_{Age} = 29.2 \pm 10.2$) from this pool participated in the experiment with highlighted targets (Target Visualization group). The other 17 participants (9 men, 8 women, $M_{Age} = 27.5 \pm 8.6$) participated in the experiment without highlighted targets (No Target Visualization group). In total 13 participants wore glasses: 9 in the target visualization and 4 in the no target visualization group.

Beforehand, participants were given an overview of the experiment and signed a written consent form. They were informed that their data would be used to help develop a gaze-based interaction interface in VR using an AI model, and their gaze data would contribute towards training a better “intention communication model” and that the current could throw errors.

3.2 Virtual reality scenario

We used Unity [Haas 2014] to create the VR scenario in a room with two screens, a table, and a robotic arm. The assets, model, and rigs were implemented using Blender [Community 2023]. In the scenario, the participant sits at the table facing the screens with the robotic arm on their right-hand side. The left-hand screen contains instructions on how the scenario will run and provides brief instructions at each step in the scenario. The right-hand screen provides information about the current trial, whether it was successful, and how many points were received.

Each trial began with the release of 11 blue and one yellow ball on predetermined points, visible to the participant on the opposite side of the table (See screenshot in figure 1). The participant is instructed to look at the yellow ball and press the touchpad on the controller. The ball that is being looked at is selected as the target.

Depending on which experimental group, the target is either highlighted by a magenta circle (Target Visualized) or it is not (Target not Visualized). After the target selection phase, the robot arm reaches forward to destroy the target. After destruction, the robot arm moves back to its starting position, passively next to the participant

To investigate system error deviating from the gaze behavior, we pseudo-randomly introduce errors throughout the experiment. The first 20% of the experiment has no system errors, the next 20% to 40% randomly introduces errors for 25% of these trials. The final 60% then has 33% of the trials randomly determined to throw errors. An error scenario happens when the system selects a different target than the one the user looked at, i.e., the system purposely selects a blue ball and not the yellow ball to destroy and the robot arm reaches towards the blue ball. The participants are not aware of when any of these errors are likely to occur.

As motivation, participants receive plus 20 points to their score if the system destroys the correct target, but they lose 20 points if the system destroys a false target. Thus, if an error is about to occur,

the participant must terminate the arm movement to prevent any low scores. Termination of the arm movement is done by pressing the trigger on the VR controller. An overview of the experimental paradigm can be found in figure 1.

Each participant starts with two training trials to learn how the system works. The gaze data and performance during training was not part of the final analysis. For the analysis, we ran 100 trials for each subject.

3.3 Virtual reality recording and data

We used VR to measure participants’ reactions to correct and incorrect feedback from the system. To interact with the VR, the participant wore the HTC Vive Pro Eye (HTC Corporation, Taoyuan, Taiwan) with built-in Tobii eye tracker (Core SW 2.16.4.67) with an accuracy estimation of $0.5^\circ - 1.1^\circ$ and a sampling frequency of 120 Hz. The Vive SRanipal SDK (HTC Corporation, Taoyuan, Taiwan) was used for calibration and to access eye tracking data [Sipatchin et al. 2021]. In addition, the participant received an HTC Vive Pro Controller 2.0.

To extract the gaze data from the VR-Headset, we used the ZERO-Interface [Hosp and Wahl 2023]. The output data contains user gaze information such as the three dimensional gaze vector and the head position, as well as information about the individual trial, such as the three dimensional spawn location of the target and whether the user canceled the trial.

3.4 Features

The overall goal is to work in a realtime system. Therefore, it is important that we have features that work in a short time window, as we have to make decisions in a short time after selecting a target. For this reason, we focus on the raw data and the features based on it without interpretation of the eye movement class (e.g. fixation, saccades). The estimated average human reaction time for pressing a button, though typically around 0.3 seconds [Deary et al. 2010], is approximated at 0.5 seconds due to potential delays in response to the randomized movement of the robotic arm. Therefore, we concentrate on the first 50 observations after the selection, i.e. on the first 50 frames after the target selection. We are looking for features that can be calculated in such a short window and that differentiate between an error and a non-error case.

We determine the gaze direction vectors given in the coordinates x, y, z and calculate the angles between the initial gaze and the subsequent gaze. With this approach, we obtain a time series that provides information on how far the gaze is moving away from the actual target. Additionally, we used the first-order deviation of the x, y and z gaze-data as proposed by [Sendhilnathan et al. 2022]

4 EVALUATION

4.1 Comparison of the conditions

Figure 2 shows a summary of the participants’ reaction to an error from the system. It is clear that the reaction to an error is much faster in the visualization case than in the non-visualization case ($t = -35.81, p < 0.001$). In addition, fewer errors are recognized in the visualized case. In the non-visualization case, many more non-errors are classified as errors by the participants. It is interesting to note that in the non-visualization condition many more errors

Figure 2: Summary of the error response. (a) shows the time to press the button in seconds when an error occurs. (b) and (c) show how the confusion matrix of error detection in the visualization and without visualization case

are classified as non-errors than in the other direction, while in the visualization case both types of misclassification occur with similar frequency. In particular, the first error, which occurs in the 22nd trial, was not correctly aborted by 82% of participants in the non-visualized scenario, while only 15% of participants in the visualized scenario failed to do so.

Providing feedback to the user about the estimated intent of the system has been shown to be a significant improvement, as the user can react more quickly in case of an error and the intention of the system can be understood more easily.

4.2 Exploratory feature analysis

For reaction to errors, we analyzed the gaze movement after target selection. As the starting point changes depending on the target

Figure 3: The progression of the average angles between the first gaze vector and the following one, with the 95% confidence interval with visual feedback. The '*'s along the x axis indicate statistically significant differences at those frame values between error and non-error ($p < 0.05$). (a) shows the summary of all subjects. (b) shows certain subjects with ideal behavior (bottom row) for model prediction and certain subjects showing the inverse (top right) or no distinguishing behavior (top left), which are harder to model.

position, we take a closer look at how far the gaze moves after the selection. Figure 3 shows the course of the angles between the first gaze direction after the selection and the following one. We also tested whether there were significant differences for each individual frame and corrected the corresponding p-values using the bonferroni correction [Weisstein 2004], which controls for the family wise error rate (FWER). We see very subject-dependent gaze behavior regarding the magnitude (size) of the reaction to error. If there is a reaction, this happens about 25 frames ($\approx 300ms$) after the target has been selected. If there is a reaction, it appears that

Figure 4: The progression of the average angles between the first gaze vector and the following one, with the 95% confidence interval for trials without visual feedback. The ‘*’s along the x axis indicate statistically significant differences at those frame values between error and non-error ($p < 0.05$). (a) shows the summary of all subjects. (b) shows certain subjects with ideal (bottom row) and non-ideal behavior (top row) for modeling.

the angle between the first gaze vector and the current gaze vector increases when an error occurs, as visible in the bottom row in figure 3b. However, this reaction can only be observed in 7 out of 20 subjects and there are also subjects for whom the reaction is reversed, as you can see in the top right image in figures 3b.

In comparison, Figure 4 shows the results for trials without visualization. There is a response in gaze to the errors, similar to the case without visualization, but here it appears between 80 and 90 frames. Meaning the reaction in gaze is distinguishable after around 1 second, while the time to press the stop button was 1.2 seconds on average. But here too, this depends heavily on the

participant as illustrated in figure 4b: nine out of 17 participants show a reaction (similar to the bottom row), nothing can be seen in other participants (similar to the top row). A similar answer is observed if focus on well known gaze features like velocity or fixation duration.

4.3 Classification with a deep learning model

Motivated by the outcome of the feature analysis, we trained a TCN to classify the error or non error case. As input, we use the first order difference of the first 40 frames after the selection, which is motivated by [Peacock et al. 2022] who have a similar setup. To train that, we used a Keras implementation from [Remy 2020]. In addition to this first-order difference approach, we tried using features such as the angles of the first 40 images as input. Overall, using the first order differences provided an accuracy of 0.701 (0.346 precision, 0.218 recall), which is just under chance (0.749). Using the features led to worse accuracy (0.655: 0.284 precision, 0.25 recall). For both approaches, we tried out a model that was trained on the first 14 participants and tested on the other five. One participant dropped out due to technical problems. We also tested each participant individually. In this case, we trained the model with the first 70 trials and tested it with the last 30 trials.

However, all models appear to have overfitting as they have an accuracy of 100% in the training set, but only TestSubj12 achieves good results in the test set. This was unexpected, as TestSubj17, for example, also shows significant differences between error and non-error cases, as shown in Figure 3b. This could be the case because there are many more non-error trials. If only a few of them have a similar course to the error trials, this is not visible in the mean value displayed in the exploratory analysis, but it can be difficult for a classifier to distinguish between them. The results for individual subjects are shown in the supplementary material.

5 DISCUSSION

This work developed a VR simulation emulating an interactive scenario with an AI-supported robotic arm to understand users’ reaction to system errors. We found that visualization of the system’s response to gaze significantly affected reaction time to system errors. Without highlighting, users were more likely to not cancel arm trajectories when there was a system error. [Rosen et al. 2020] found similar collision stopping behavior with a highlighted interface for robotic arm manipulation, though they did not measure gaze. User gaze coupled with system visualizations can inform them of corrections to eye tracker precision errors [Sidenmark et al. 2022], helping users better understand a system’s capabilities. Here, we show that an assisted-robotic scenario can also benefit from visualizing how the system interprets the gaze rather than showing gaze in realtime. This can promote more timely corrections to the robot’s planned actions. Considering realistic scenarios, for example using AR, if a user with mobility constraints intends to grasp a cup of tea, and the system incorrectly highlights another object, an embarrassing situation can be quickly avoided.

Our second contribution investigated how to better evaluate the perceptual and motor response to errors. We found that with some participants after a target was selected, there were gaze differences that are visible before they would press the button to stop. This was

the case for both with/ without visualization of the selected target. Though, eye movement differences showed faster error recognition when the system provided visualization: Around 300ms into the planned arm movement. In similar scenarios where automated systems can react unexpectedly for users, such as pilots in a cockpit, automatically predicting this “surprise” effect could help avoid complications by triggering a timely warning [Dehais et al. 2015]. Fast detection of system error through the user’s raw gaze stream can support interfaces when other modalities lose signal or higher order information (saccades, pupil information, spatial information, etc.) are susceptible to processing constraints.

Our third contribution is our most unfortunate. Inspired by [Sendhilkathan et al. 2022], we trained a TCN with gaze features as predictors to determine system errors in an online setup. We used event features based on [Peacock et al. 2022] and the first order differences. Performance for both inputs showed around chance level, with overfitting on the training data. We found that gaze behavior was very subject-dependent, which proved complex for automatic classification. Further investigation is needed to determine why we could not achieve good performance with this approach. Our initial assumption could be our unbalanced dataset with primarily non-error trials, and we did not have enough data for undersampling. However, a potentially more fitting direction for this research could investigate continuous learning based models. In reality, system errors should be minimal and models that exploit a deviation from the *standard operating gaze* can improve for each user over time. By incorporating realtime feedback and adjusting parameters with each interaction, the model not only adapts to individual users’ unique gaze patterns but also gains the ability to generalize and enhance its performance across diverse user scenarios.

6 CONCLUSION

Recognizing the potential of AI in enhancing mobility devices, the latest systems show that they can handle complex user input. To evaluate this progress, we developed a VR environment to measure participants’ reactions to correct and incorrect feedback generated by an AI-powered system. The objective was to determine the AI system’s capacity to automatically predict occurring errors in user’s gaze in a short time frame. We employed quickly recognizable gaze features as a potential tool for evaluating user responses. These features include the angle between an initial gaze vector and the subsequent ones as well as eye movements events. To understand the nuances of developing a universally applicable model for real-time input error detection, we examined subject-dependent gaze behavior. The use of TCNs for this purpose, which was based on previous work, proved difficult, highlighting the challenges in creating a one-size-fits-all solution. We advocate for the exploration of more adaptable models tailored to individual users, providing a potentially more effective approach for the development of gaze-based accessibility systems. This perspective recognizes the underlying variability of user responses and aims to improve the overall usability and effectiveness of AI-driven mobility systems.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This research is supported by European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No.951910

and the German Research Foundation (DFG): SFB 1233, Robust Vision: Inference Principles and Neural Mechanisms, TP TRA, project No. 276693517.

REFERENCES

- Julia Andras, Elio Mazzone, Fijis WB van Leeuwen, Geert De Naeyer, Matthias N van Oosterom, Sergi Beato, Tessa Buckle, Shane O’Sullivan, Pim J van Leeuwen, Alexander Beulens, et al. 2020. Artificial intelligence and robotics: a combination that is changing the operating room. *World journal of urology* 38 (2020), 2359–2366.
- Reuben M. Aronson and Henny Admoni. 2018. Gaze for error detection during human-robot shared manipulation.
- Michael Barz, Florian Daiber, Daniel Sonntag, and Andreas Bulling. 2018. Error-aware gaze-based interfaces for robust mobile gaze interaction. In *Proceedings of the 2018 ACM Symposium on Eye Tracking Research & Applications*. 1–10.
- Kenan Bektaş, Jannis Strecker, Simon Mayer, Dr Kimberly Garcia, Jonas Hermann, Kay Erik Jenss, Yasmine Sheila Antille, and Marc Solèr. 2023. GEAR: Gaze-enabled augmented reality for human activity recognition. In *Proceedings of the 2023 Symposium on Eye Tracking Research and Applications*. 1–9.
- Anna Belardinelli. 2023. Gaze-based intention estimation: principles, methodologies, and applications in HRI. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2302.04530* (2023).
- Serena Booth, James Tompkin, Hanspeter Pfister, Jim Waldo, Krzysztof Gajos, and Radhika Nagpal. 2017. Piggybacking Robots: Human-Robot Overtrust in University Dormitory Security (*HRI ’17*). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 426–434. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2909824.3020211>
- Riccardo Bovo, Nicola Binetti, Duncan P Brumby, and Simon Julier. 2020. Detecting errors in pick and place procedures: detecting errors in multi-stage and sequence-constrained manual retrieve-assembly procedures. In *Proceedings of the 25th International Conference on Intelligent User Interfaces*. 536–545.
- Carmen Bruder, Paul Weber, and Catrin Hasse. 2016. To Look and (Not) See: Predicting the Detection of Automation Failures Based on the Eye Movements of Human Operators. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Human-Computer Interaction in Aerospace* (Paris, France) (*HCI-Aero ’16*). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 5, 7 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2950112.2964579>
- Blender Online Community. 2023. *Blender - a 3D modelling and rendering package*. Blender Foundation, Stichting Blender Foundation, Amsterdam. <http://www.blender.org>
- Brendan David-John, Candace Peacock, Ting Zhang, T Scott Murdison, Hrvoje Benko, and Tanya R Jonker. 2021. Towards gaze-based prediction of the intent to interact in virtual reality. In *ACM Symposium on Eye Tracking Research and Applications*. 1–7.
- Ian Deary, David (Dave) Liewald, and Jack Nissan. 2010. A free, easy-to-use, computer-based simple and four-choice reaction time programme: The Deary-Liewald reaction time task. *Behavior research methods* 43 (11 2010), 258–68. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13428-010-0024-1>
- Frederic Dehais, Vsevolod Peysakhovich, Sébastien Scannella, Jennifer Fongue, and Thibault Gateau. 2015. “Automation Surprise” in Aviation: Real-Time Solutions. In *Proceedings of the 33rd annual ACM conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. 2525–2534.
- John K Haas. 2014. A history of the unity game engine. (2014).
- Teresa Hirzle, Maurice Cordts, Enrico Rukzio, and Andreas Bulling. 2020. A survey of digital eye strain in gaze-based interactive systems. In *ACM Symposium on Eye Tracking Research and Applications*. 1–12.
- Benedikt W. Hosp and Siegfried Wahl. 2023. ZERO: A Generic Open-Source Extended Reality Eye-Tracking Controller Interface for Scientists. In *Proceedings of the 2023 Symposium on Eye Tracking Research and Applications* (Tubingen, Germany) (*ETRA ’23*). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 64, 4 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3588015.3589203>
- Rob Jacob and Sophie Stellmach. 2016. What you look at is what you get: gaze-based user interfaces. *interactions* 23, 5 (2016), 62–65.
- Robert JK Jacob and Keith S Karn. 2003. Eye tracking in human-computer interaction and usability research: Ready to deliver the promises. In *The mind’s eye*. Elsevier, 573–605.
- Bing Cai Kok and Harold Soh. 2020. Trust in Robots: Challenges and Opportunities. *Current robotics reports* 1, 4 (2020), 297–309. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43154-020-00029-y>
- Moritz Körber, Eva Baseler, and Klaus Bengler. 2018. Introduction matters: Manipulating trust in automation and reliance in automated driving. *Applied Ergonomics* 66 (2018), 18–31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apergo.2017.07.006>
- Min Hun Lee, Daniel P Siewiorek, Asim Smailagic, Alexandre Bernardino, and Sergi Bermúdez i Badia. 2022. Enabling AI and robotic coaches for physical rehabilitation therapy: iterative design and evaluation with therapists and post-stroke survivors. *International Journal of Social Robotics* (2022), 1–22.
- Benedikt Leichtmann, Andreas Hinterreiter, Christina Humer, Marc Streit, and Martina Mara. 2023. Explainable Artificial Intelligence Improves Human Decision-Making: Results from a Mushroom Picking Experiment at a Public Art Festival. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction* 0, 0 (2023), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/>

- 10447318.2023.2221605 arXiv:<https://doi.org/10.1080/10447318.2023.2221605>
- Olga Lukashova-Sanz, Rajat Agarwala, and Siegfried Wahl. 2022. Context matters during pick-and-place in VR: Impact on search and transport phases. *Frontiers in Psychology* 13 (2022), 881269.
- Päivi Majaranta and Kari-Jouko Rähä. 2002. Twenty years of eye typing: systems and design issues. In *Proceedings of the 2002 symposium on Eye tracking research & applications*. 15–22.
- Gloria Mark and Alfred Kobsa. 2005. The Effects of Collaboration and System Transparency on CIVE Usage: An Empirical Study and Model. *Presence* 14, 1 (2005), 60–80. <https://doi.org/10.1162/1054746053890279>
- Mohsen Parisay, Charalambos Poullis, and Marta Kersten-Oertel. 2020. Felix: Fixation-based eye fatigue load index a multi-factor measure for gaze-based interactions. In *2020 13th International Conference on Human System Interaction (HSI)*. IEEE, 74–81.
- Candace E. Peacock, Ben Lafreniere, Ting Zhang, Stephanie Santosa, Hrvoje Benko, and Tanya R. Jonker. 2022. Gaze as an Indicator of Input Recognition Errors. *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.* 6, ETRA, Article 142 (may 2022), 18 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3530883>
- Anna Penzkofer, Simon Schaefer, Florian Strohm, Mihai Băce, Stefan Leutenegger, and Andreas Bulling. 2023. Int-HRL: Towards Intention-based Hierarchical Reinforcement Learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2306.11483* (2023).
- Philippe Remy. 2020. Temporal Convolutional Networks for Keras. <https://github.com/philipperemy/keras-ten>.
- Eric Rosen, David Whitney, Elizabeth Phillips, Gary Chien, James Tompkin, George Konidaris, and Stefanie Tellex. 2020. Communicating robot arm motion intent through mixed reality head-mounted displays. In *Robotics Research: The 18th International Symposium ISRR*. Springer, 301–316.
- Yuki Sakai, Huimin Lu, Joo-Kooi Tan, and Hyoungseop Kim. 2019. Recognition of surrounding environment from electric wheelchair videos based on modified YOLOv2. *Future Generation Computer Systems* 92 (2019), 157–161.
- Naveen Sindhinathan, Ting Zhang, Ben Lafreniere, Tovi Grossman, and Tanya R. Jonker. 2022. Detecting Input Recognition Errors and User Errors Using Gaze Dynamics in Virtual Reality. In *Proceedings of the 35th Annual ACM Symposium on User Interface Software and Technology* (Bend, OR, USA) (*UIST '22*). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 38, 19 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3526113.3545628>
- Björn Severitt, Nora Jane Castner, Olga Lukashova-Sanz, and Siegfried Wahl. 2023. Leveraging Gaze for Potential Error Prediction in AI-Support Systems: An Exploratory Analysis of Interaction with a Simulated Robot. In *Companion Publication of the 25th International Conference on Multimodal Interaction* (, Paris, France,) (*ICMI '23 Companion*). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 56–60. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3610661.3617163>
- Ludwig Sidenmark, Mark Parent, Chi-Hao Wu, Joannes Chan, Michael Glueck, Daniel Wigdor, Tovi Grossman, and Marcello Giordano. 2022. Weighted Pointer: Error-aware Gaze-based Interaction through Fallback Modalities. *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics* 28, 11 (2022), 3585–3595.
- Alexandra Sipatchin, Siegfried Wahl, and Katharina Rifai. 2021. Eye-Tracking for Clinical Ophthalmology with Virtual Reality (VR): A Case Study of the HTC Vive Pro Eye's Usability. *Healthcare* 9, 2 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare9020180>
- Mahendran Subramanian, Noyan Songur, Darrell Adjei, Pavel Orlov, and A Aldo Faisal. 2019. A. Eye Drive: Gaze-based semi-autonomous wheelchair interface. In *2019 41st annual international conference of the IEEE engineering in medicine and biology society (EMBC)*. IEEE, 5967–5970.
- Ker-Jiun Wang, Quanbo Liu, Yifan Zhao, Caroline Yan Zheng, Soumya Vhasure, Quanfeng Liu, Prakash Thakur, Mingui Sun, and Zhi-Hong Mao. 2018. Intelligent wearable virtual reality (VR) gaming controller for people with motor disabilities. In *2018 IEEE International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Virtual Reality (AIVR)*. IEEE, 161–164.
- Eric W Weisstein. 2004. Bonferroni correction. [https://mathworld.wolfram.com/\(2004\)](https://mathworld.wolfram.com/(2004)).
- Feng Wen, Zixuan Zhang, Tianyiyi He, and Chengkuo Lee. 2021. AI enabled sign language recognition and VR space bidirectional communication using triboelectric smart glove. *Nature communications* 12, 1 (2021), 5378.
- Walid Zgallai, John Teye Brown, Afnan Ibrahim, Fatma Mahmood, Khulood Mohamad, Maitha Khalfan, Maryam Mohammed, Maryam Salem, and Noof Hamood. 2019. Deep learning AI application to an EEG driven BCI smart wheelchair. In *2019 Advances in Science and Engineering Technology International Conferences (ASET)*. IEEE, 1–5.
- Xiao-Yun Zhou, Yao Guo, Mali Shen, and Guang-Zhong Yang. 2020. Application of artificial intelligence in surgery. *Frontiers of medicine* 14 (2020), 417–430.
- Chang Zhu, Quan Liu, Wei Meng, Qingsong Ai, and Sheng Q Xie. 2021. An attention-based cnn-lstm model with limb synergy for joint angles prediction. In *2021 IEEE/ASME International Conference on Advanced Intelligent Mechatronics (AIM)*. IEEE, 747–752.